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PHARMACOECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF AUTOLOGOUS (NATIVE) TISSUE SURGICAL TECHNIQUES IN THE TREATMENT OF PELVIC ORGAN PROLAPSE**Yuldashev S.K.**Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center for Maternal and Child Health,
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Resume. Pelvic organ prolapse (POP) is one of the most common gynecological conditions and imposes a substantial economic burden on health systems, largely because of the high rate of recurrence and reoperation after standard surgical correction. This study presents a cost-minimization (pharmacoeconomic) analysis comparing two modified autologous (native) tissue techniques — laparoscopic correction of post-hysterectomy apical prolapse and nourishing-flap reconstruction of the central anterior vaginal wall defect — with standard surgical treatment that uses synthetic materials. The analysis was based on the direct medical cost of primary treatment, the documented one-year recurrence rate of the standard methods (approximately 20–21 %, requiring reoperation in about one in five patients) and the absence of recurrence after the proposed techniques during 12 months of follow-up. Although each native-tissue technique increased the cost of the primary operation only marginally (by 22 000 and 87 000 UZS per case, i.e. about 0.5–1.9 %), the elimination of recurrence-driven rehospitalization and reoperation produced a net saving of approximately 927 289 UZS and 846 650 UZS per patient per year, respectively. The findings indicate that, despite a negligible increase in upfront cost, native-tissue reconstruction is economically advantageous and additionally avoids the costs associated with mesh-related complications.

Keywords: pelvic organ prolapse, pharmacoeconomics, cost-minimization analysis, native tissue repair, recurrence, reoperation, mesh-free surgery, health economics.

ЧАНОҚ АЪЗОЛАРИ ПРОЛАПСИНИ БЕМОРНИНГ ЎЗ (НАТИВ) ТЎҚИМАЛАРИ ЁРДАМИДА ЖАРРОҲЛИК ДАВОЛАШ УСУЛЛАРИНИНГ ФАРМАКОИҚТИСОДИЙ ТАҲЛИЛИ**Юлдашев С.К.**Республика ихтисослаштирилган она ва бола саломатлиги илмий-амалий тиббиёт маркази,
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Резюме. Чаноқ аъзолари пролапси (ЧАП) — энг кенг тарқалган гинекологик касалликлардан бири бўлиб, стандарт жарроҳлик коррекциясидан кейинги юқори қайталаниш ва такрорий операциялар туфайли соғлиқни сақлаш тизимида сезиларли иқтисодий юк солади. Ушбу ишда беморнинг ўз (натив) тўқималаридан фойдаланган икки модификацияланган усул — постгистерэктомик апикал пролапси лапароскопик тузатиш ва қин олдинги девори марказий нуқсонини озиқлантирувчи лоскут билан реконструкция қилиш — синтетик материаллар қўлланиладиган стандарт жарроҳлик даволаш билан таққосланган харажатларни минималлаштириш (фармакоиқтисодий) таҳлили келтирилган. Таҳлил бирламчи даволашнинг тўғридан-тўғри тиббий харажатларига, стандарт усулларнинг хужжатлаштирилган йиллик қайталаниш даражасига (тахминан 20–21 %, ҳар бешинчи беморда такрорий операцияни талаб қилади) ва таклиф этилган усуллардан кейин 12 ой давомида қайталаниш кузатилмаганлигига асосланди. Ҳар бир натив-тўқима усули бирламчи операция нарҳини жуда оз (мос равишда 22 000 ва 87 000 сўмга, яъни тахминан 0,5–1,9 %) оширган бўлса-да, қайталаниш сабабли такрорий госпитализация ва операцияларнинг бартараф этилиши бир беморга йилига тахминан 927 289 сўм ва 846 650 сўм соф иқтисод қилиш имконини берди. Натижалар шуни кўрсатадики, бирламчи харажатларнинг арзимас ошишига қарамай, ўз тўқималари билан реконструкция иқтисодий жиҳатдан афзал ва қўшимча равишда тўрли имплантлар асоратлари билан боғлиқ харажатларни ҳам бартараф этади.

Калит сўзлар: чаноқ аъзолари пролапси, фармакоиқтисод, харажатларни минималлаштириш таҳлили, ўз тўқималари билан пластика, қайталаниш, такрорий операция, тўрсиз жарроҳлик, соғлиқни сақлаш иқтисоди.

ФАРМАКОЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ ХИРУРГИЧЕСКИХ МЕТОДИК ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ПРОЛАПСА ТАЗОВЫХ ОРГАНОВ С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ СОБСТВЕННЫХ (НАТИВНЫХ) ТКАНЕЙ

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Резюме. Пропалс тазовых органов (ПТО) является одним из наиболее распространённых гинекологических заболеваний и создаёт существенную экономическую нагрузку на систему здравоохранения, главным образом из-за высокой частоты рецидивов и повторных операций после стандартной хирургической коррекции. В работе представлен анализ минимизации затрат (фармакоэкономический анализ), сравнивающий две модифицированные методики с использованием собственных (нативных) тканей — лапароскопическую коррекцию постгистерэктомиического апикального пролапса и реконструкцию центрального дефекта передней стенки влагалища питающим лоскутом — со стандартным хирургическим лечением с применением синтетических материалов. Анализ основывался на прямых медицинских затратах первичного лечения, документированной годовой частоте рецидивов стандартных методов (около 20–21 %, требующей повторной операции примерно у каждой пятой пациентки) и отсутствии рецидивов после предложенных методик в течение 12 месяцев наблюдения. Хотя каждая нативно-тканевая методика лишь незначительно повышала стоимость первичной операции (на 22 000 и 87 000 сум на случай, т.е. около 0,5–1,9 %), устранение обусловленных рецидивами повторных госпитализаций и операций обеспечило чистую экономию примерно 927 289 сум и 846 650 сум на пациентку в год соответственно. Результаты показывают, что, несмотря на незначительное увеличение первоначальных затрат, реконструкция собственными тканями экономически выгодна и дополнительно исключает расходы, связанные с осложнениями сетчатых имплантов.

Ключевые слова: пролапс тазовых органов, фармакоэкономика, анализ минимизации затрат, пластика собственными тканями, рецидив, повторная операция, бессеточная хирургия, экономика здравоохранения.

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Introduction. Pelvic organ prolapse (POP) is among the most prevalent gynecological disorders, and its frequency rises with age and with the ageing of the population. According to the World Health Organization, at least 40 million women are affected by postpartum prolapse each year, and the number of women living with POP is projected to reach approximately 63 million by 2030. Prevalence reaches 30–40 % in women over 40 years and 50–60 % in women over 60 years. Because only a minority of affected women (10–20 %) seek medical care, the condition is both a major medical and a major social problem.

Surgery remains the only definitive treatment for symptomatic prolapse. However, standard surgical correction is associated with a high rate of recurrence: up to one third of patients require repeat surgery, and this proportion shows no tendency to decline. Recurrence and reoperation, together with the cost of synthetic mesh and of managing mesh-related complications (erosion, chronic pelvic pain, infection), make POP surgery one of the costliest areas of gynecology. Following restrictions on transvaginal mesh by regulatory bodies such as the U.S. Food and Drug Administration, attention has shifted toward organ-preserving reconstruction using the patient's own (native) tissues.

Two modified native-tissue techniques have been developed and introduced into clinical practice: a laparoscopic technique for correcting post-hysterectomy apical prolapse using autologous tissue, and a nourishing-flap technique for reconstructing the central defect of the anterior vaginal wall. In prospective comparative studies, both techniques achieved complete anatomical restoration and showed no recurrence during 12 months of follow-up, in contrast to the standard methods. While the clinical effectiveness of these techniques has been documented, their economic value has not been assessed separately. Given the high cost of recurrence and reoperation, a pharmacoeconomic evaluation is essential to justify their wider adoption. The aim of the present study was therefore to perform a cost-minimization analysis comparing the two native-tissue techniques with standard surgical treatment.

Materials and Methods. This pharmacoeconomic study used a cost-minimization analysis (CMA), which is appropriate when the compared interventions provide at least equivalent clinical effectiveness — a condition satisfied here, because both native-tissue techniques were at least as effective as standard surgery and were associated with no recurrence. The analysis was based on prospective comparative clinical data

obtained at the Department of Operative Gynecology of the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center for Maternal and Child Health (Tashkent) between 2022 and 2024.

Only direct medical costs were considered. The cost of inpatient surgical treatment per patient (S) was calculated as $S = Ab \times (Tm + Z)$, where Ab is the number of bed-days, Tm is the cost of treatment per patient (the sum of drug-therapy cost and consumable/material cost), and Z is the associated staffing and overhead cost. The per-patient cost was determined separately for the standard method and for each proposed native-tissue method.

The economic effect of each native-tissue technique was then derived by comparing (a) the marginal increase in the cost of the primary operation with (b) the avoided cost of recurrence-driven rehospitalization and reoperation. Recurrence rates were taken from the 12-month follow-up of the comparison (standard-treatment) groups, in which approximately one in five patients (about 20–21 %) required reoperation within one year, whereas no recurrences were recorded after either native-tissue technique. All costs are expressed in Uzbek soum (UZS). The cost components and the resulting one-year economic effect are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1.

Cost components and one-year economic effect of the native-tissue techniques versus standard surgical treatment (per patient)

Parameter	Apical — standard	Apical — native tissue	Anterior wall — standard	Anterior wall — native flap
Drug therapy + materials (Tm), UZS	3 854 000	3 876 000	3 752 000	3 864 000
Staffing / overhead (Z), UZS	820 000	820 000	820 000	820 000
Cost per primary case (S), UZS	4 674 000	4 696 000	4 597 000	4 684 000
Marginal cost vs standard, UZS	—	+22 000	—	+87 000
1-year recurrence / reoperation	≈20.3 %	0 %	≈21.3 %	0 %
Net effect per patient / year, UZS	—	927 289	—	846 650

Results. The per-patient cost of the standard treatment was 4 674 000 UZS for apical prolapse and 4 597 000 UZS for the central anterior wall defect. The corresponding native-tissue techniques cost 4 696 000 UZS and 4 684 000 UZS per patient — only 22 000 UZS (about 0.5 %) and 87 000 UZS (about 1.9 %) more, respectively. Thus, the additional outlay for performing the proposed operations on 100 patients amounted to 2 200 000 UZS and 8 700 000 UZS.

This marginal increase was offset by the elimination of recurrences. With the standard methods, reoperation was required in approximately one in five patients within 12 months, at a rehospitalization-and-reoperation cost per patient comparable to that of the primary admission. For every 100 patients, the recurrence-driven reoperation burden of the standard approach therefore reached the order of 90–95 million UZS per year. Because the native-tissue techniques produced no recurrences over 12 months, this burden was avoided.

After subtracting the marginal increase in the cost of the primary operation from the avoided reoperation cost, the net economic effect of the laparoscopic apical native-tissue technique was approximately 92.7 million UZS per 100 patients, equivalent to 927 289 UZS per patient per year. For the anterior-wall nourishing-flap technique, the net economic effect was approximately 84.7 million UZS per 100 patients, equivalent to 846 650 UZS per patient per year. In both cases the increase in the cost of the primary intervention was below 2 %, while the savings from avoided reoperations were an order of magnitude larger.

Beyond these calculated savings, the native-tissue approach avoids the purchase cost of synthetic mesh and the cost of managing mesh-specific complications such as erosion, chronic pelvic pain, and infection, including the repeat reconstructive surgery that such complications often require. The shorter operative time and reduced blood loss observed with the proposed techniques further lower intraoperative resource use.

Conclusion. The cost-minimization analysis shows that autologous (native) tissue reconstruction of pelvic organ prolapse is economically advantageous compared with standard surgical treatment. Although each proposed technique increased the cost of the primary operation by less than 2 %, the elimination of recurrence-driven reoperations yielded a net saving of approximately 927 289 UZS per patient per year for the

laparoscopic apical technique and 846 650 UZS per patient per year for the anterior-wall nourishing-flap technique. The mesh-free nature of both techniques additionally removes the costs associated with synthetic implants and their complications. These findings support the wider implementation of native-tissue reconstruction as a clinically effective and cost-saving strategy for the surgical treatment of pelvic organ prolapse.

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